

Impossible Fibers viscometer lab equipment guide

Model: Brookfield Ametek DVNext Viscometer

Version: 1.0

Author: Wade Ingram

Date: 2/23/2026

For detailed operation, the user guide provided by Brookfield Engineering can be found [here](#).

1. Turn on the viscometer using the power switch in the back

2. When the system comes online, it will show a blue screen for ~5 seconds before automatically reaching the "Auto Zero" start page.
3. The spindle should still be in its case, so press next on the screen to allow for the auto zero of the system.
4. When it is complete press next.

5. The screen that it pulls up next is from the main menu for “Configure Viscosity Test”. From this menu you can run a viscosity measurement if you know the approximate viscosity of your solution and the conditions (spindle speed) needed.

6. If you don't know what viscosity range or appropriate measurement conditions, press the home button in the top left corner and select “Viscosity Wizard”

7. This option will help you to create a run that works for your system. It allows you to select comparative liquids to the test liquid so you can get a measurement of your sample and builds the testing inputs that are needed.
8. Whether using the “Viscosity Wizard” or “Configure Viscosity Test” option, when you have determined the conditions for your test, to load a sample you need to remove the bottom cup by moving the metal stopping rod holding it in place. Use one hand to hold the cup and the other to move the rod so that you don’t drop the cup.
9. When the cup is removed, determine which spindle you want to use for measuring the viscosity of your samples. The 40Z spindle is meant for viscosities from 0.15cP to 3000cP and the 52Z spindle is able to characterize high viscosity solutions from 4.6cP to 92,000cP.
10. The spindles attach to the rheometer magnetically, so you only need to adjust them so the base lines up and it will hold into place.

11. Reattach the cup, and move the metal rod back under to support the sample cup.
12. Now select "Set Cone Plate Gap". From this menu, follow the instructions as prompted, but in short, twist the upper adjustment ring which has references along its surface until the screen lights up yellow (clockwise lowers the cup, while counterclockwise raises it).
 - a. If it is already yellow, adjust the cup until the icon turns white.
13. Continue moving the micrometer adjusting ring slowly counterclockwise until the yellow light indicating contact first turns on. This is the "Hit Point".

14. Using the adjustment marks on the upper ring, make note of where the contact point is and move the adjustment ring one full division clockwise, which should make the yellow hit indicator go off (turn white), establishing the correct gap space (0.0005 in). Press ok.
15. Very carefully, remove the cup and dispense 0.5mL of the solution you want to measure the viscosity of directly into the center of the cup, which will be below the spindle.
16. Attach the sample cup and allow for the system to equilibrate if there is a temperature difference.
17. Double check the parameters, and set them if you didn't do the "Viscosity Wizard" page, and then click "Run"
18. Record data from the run
19. When finished, remove the cup and clean it using soap and water and then wipe with a kimwipe with 70% IPA and dry it. Do the same with the spindle, and put it back in the correct case for it. Reattach the cup.
20. Turn off the power.